

METHODS USED IN PEDAGOGICAL ACMEOLOGY

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Annotation: In the article, the acmeographic method makes it possible to obtain scientific results at the level, about personal and professional development, acmeographic description is the basis of preliminary preparation, about the fact that a part of the acmeogram corresponds to the general and level of having an internal structure that reflects the structure of professional skills. considered.

Key words: acmeology, psychological methods, diagnosis, acmeological analysis, acmeological expertise, acmeogram.

Introduction:

Acmeology develops as a science of human dignity, its improvement, and the ability not only to perform one's professional duties at a high level, but also to lead a fulfilling life. This implies a deeper study of objective and subjective factors that help or hinder the advanced development of a mature person as a subject of life in general, not just professional activity.

Modern acmeology is aimed at solving the problem of proportionality, social and life changes in personal life, human characteristics.

Accordingly, the object and subject of acmeology can be defined and defined. Acmeological, acmeocentric and development of acmeographic approaches led to the logical creation of real acmeological methods. The acmeological method is a set of enabling techniques, methods of action. Acmeographic method, acmeographic approach, as developed within a special type of acmeological method. Acmeographic method allows obtaining scientific results at the level of application: general, specific and individual.

With the help of acmeographic method, acmeographic descriptions are developed. If the speech is about progressive personal and professional development, acmeographic description is the basis of preliminary preparation. Part of the acmeogram corresponds to the general and level. This activity is based on acmeographic descriptions and relies on the concepts of professionalism of the person.

Materials:

Such descriptions are usually presented in the following form (qualitatively strict description). The existing functional relationships with distinction and description must also have an internal structure that reflects the theory. The

thoughts about the described phenomenon, especially the generalization of acmeological research on the development problem, allow to emphasize the professionalism of the activity. The following components are of particular importance in highlighting such acmeographic description:

- increase professional competence;
- improvement of professional skills and qualifications;
- adopting new methods of adoption and implementation of effective solutions;
- development of new high-performance algorithms and technologies for solving professional problems;
- improvement of the self-control system;
- development of new technical means of activity.

It is necessary to describe the content of these components, including normative indicators of their level. Similarly, in the substructure of professional development, it is necessary to describe the person:

- general acmeological formation and development invariants of professionalism;
- important professional qualities of personal, business and psychological development;
- increased need for self-awareness and achievement, expansion of horizons;
- reveal the creative potential of a person.

Unlike the acmeographic description, which is carried out at the general and special level, the acmeogram requires only the reflection of the individual level.

In other words, an acmeogram is always individual, it is "someone's", that is, it belongs to a certain subject and does not correspond to another. Acmeogram is the basis for individuality, personal and professional development, professional high level - this is usually "production of one product". Any acmeogram is always individual, its development should be carried out according to a single standard. In the developed standard scheme, acmeograms have sections related to levels:

- general (*substructures of professional qualifications, general acmeological invariants of professionalism*), assessment of their compliance with certain requirements;
- special (*substructures of a special person's direction are physical acmeological invariants of professionalism*);

➤ single (*substructures of abilities, character traits, moral qualities, etc.*) is its main part.

In this sense, the acmeogram partly intersects with the acmeographic description, but these intersections are also "individual" in relation to the subject of development.

The development of acmeograms requires a very high level of expertise. Being fluent in the instrumental and many methods of non-instrumental psychodiagnostics that developed it, having practical experience, a psychologist with developed intuition, helps to "feel" the developing dynamic features. It can be said that a mature person, respect for the person, solving tasks for him is extremely important and responsible.

Currently, in acmeological practice, it is used to develop an acmeogram of the following typical scheme of personal and professional development.

Practice shows that when drawing a person, acmeograms must meet a number of important conditions. Acmeogram must necessarily include goals personal and professional development (*final and intermediate*). In acmeographic examination, it is necessary to apply various methods - test, cross-examination, observation, interviews, surveys, etc. Acmeologist, using them, must confirm their high qualification. Care in special work should be indicated in the characterological description. Personal characteristics and moral qualities - no mistake is allowed here.

Acmeographic descriptions can vary in quality from rigorous to quantitative, including direct measurements and evaluation data. If necessary, they can be shortened without a single size rating system. It is desirable to present the results of acmeographic description in the form of a functional diagram.

According to the results of the acmeographic examination, it is necessary to emphasize the dynamics of the growth of professional skills; "bottlenecks", i.e. conditions and factors that prevent growth; characteristics of changes in the motivational field; the dynamics of personal development and what helps or hinders it; It is recommended to apply for the type of acmeological technologies for personal and professional development.

Conclusion:

An acmeographic description and an acmeogram are required and must include individual recommendations. The developed acmeogram should be the basis for personal and professional development monitoring, comparative analysis at the main stages of development in order to create a new goal.

According to available information, such acmeograms were created for certain categories of military specialists, civil servants, teachers, representatives of some types of creative professions.

Acmeographic descriptions and acmeograms as acmeological methods are constantly being improved. Therefore, the improvement from the presented options was mainly done through simplification, which is still a very laborious method now.

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